

Effect Of Gender And Department On Motivation, Self-Efficacy, And Perception As Teacher Of Pre-Service Teacher Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 05, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 04, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Gender, Department, Motivation, Self-efficacy, Pre-service teacher student</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4902177</p>	<p><i>The number of female teacher candidates dominates teacher education schools. They dominated the social humanity department. It is feasible to question quality motivation, self-efficacy, and perception as teachers whether it is better to compare male students, it also applies to the perspective of the department. Therefore, a comparative study was conducted. This study involved 758 students filling google form in voluntary scale form. The scale has three types, namely, motivation scale as teacher, efficacy scale as a teacher, and perception scale as a teacher. The data were analyzed by two-way analysis of variance. The results indicate that there were differences in motivation as a teacher, efficacy as a teacher, and perception as a teacher between female and male students. The female students had higher motivation as a teacher, efficacy as a teacher, and perception as a teacher than the male ones. It also applied to social humanity students with exact science students. Female students with the social humanity department had the best motivation as a teacher, efficacy as a teacher, and perception as a teacher, followed by male students with social humanity, female students with exact science, and male students with an exact science.</i></p>

Introduction

Recognition of rights to get an education in Indonesia for each citizen has been assured in Paragraph 1 of Article 1 of the 1945 Constitution, stating that each citizen has rights to get an education, it also applies to Law Number 39/1999 concerning Human Rights (HR), complying with Article 12. In this reference, the Indonesian government has given equal opportunity and rights to all Indonesian male and female citizens to take education from primary school to university. In the past time, female students did have limited access to educational facilities. Today, the problem does not occur, signed by a relatively balanced participation rate between males (9%) and females (9.52%) (Kemenristekdikti, 2019). However, sociological and cultural perspectives progressing in the community are still questionable and become a motivator of change in access and equality harmony having developed in the educational world (Fuller, 2009). For example, patriarchal opinion frequently poisons and destructs education for the females (Ratnawati, Sulistyorini, and Abidin, 2019).

In the current condition, female students dominate the Teaching Education Institution (LPTK), and the majority (60%) of female students graduated (Kemenristekdikti, 2019). It seems consistent with total teachers registered in 2020 also dominated by females. Total teachers were 3,247,351 individuals, consisting of 974,709 (30.02%) male teachers, and 2,272,642 (69.98%) female teachers. Therefore, this condition resulted in questions, especially from an internal aspect, namely, was perception as teachers, self-efficacy as teachers, and motivation as teachers of females were better than males? Likewise, from the perspectives of the department, the males and females have unique interests. For example, the females have a lower participation rate in mathematic than males; likewise, the number of females is lower than the males in careers as mathematic professionals. However, females dominate historic science (Bank, 2007). Therefore, the fact indicates that phenomena have a different tendency. It is attractive to express; moreover, if it is seen from the interaction between department and gender.

Role and gender career

From the starting, biologically individual difference between the males and females has explained role and task. Nevertheless, along with individual development and social need, gender roles appear (Bank, 2007). Therefore, gender roles are dynamic. Gender roles have characteristics: these are the learned behaviors, can change along with time, maybe different from cultures, differ from traditions, can be relational, hierarchy, institutional, and specific context (UNESCO, 2015). Each citizen gives roles to males and females based on social needs and

perception. Roles often reflect reliance and public economic, cultural, religious, and political teachings. Although many cultures will have similar roles to the males and females, the attribution of roles in specific cultures may be different (UNESCO, 2015).

Perception as teachers

Perception is the sorting, interpretation, analysis, and integration of stimulations that sense and brain organs make (Feldman, 2011). Like other psychological concepts, perception also requires an object. In this study, the object is the teacher. Therefore, perception as a teacher includes selection as competency to teach what is felt, interpretation, analysis, and integration of intrinsic career values, as well as personal utility values (job assurance, time for family, and ability of work transfer) and social values. Thus, the variability of perception as a teacher is very opened, from competency to teach what is felt (Samuelsson and Samuelsson, 2016), interpretation of teacher profession, analysis of teacher task, and integration of intrinsic career values (Nzilano, 2013), as well as personal and social benefit values (Shinde and Karekatti, 2012). Thus, perception as a teacher is perception consisting of development to explore attributes of teacher profession, and process information of various individual stimulation components, which are interpretation, analysis, and integration of intrinsic, personal and social values of teacher profession, then changing and moving to be overall perception (Feldman, 2011). The process to establish perception as a teacher in students of teacher candidates widely occur in their educational age (Pop, 2015).

Self-efficacy as teacher

Self-efficacy is the self-reliance of an individual regarding competency to manage, implement a task, and apply action to achieve specific success (Bandura, 1997). Therefore, self-efficacy becomes very important because whether it will participate in determining a student's success in becoming a professional teacher or not (Schunk and DiBenedetto, 2016). Efficacy as a teacher includes efficacy in a learning strategy, efficacy in classroom management, and efficacy in student engagement (Tschannen-Moran and Hoy, 2001).

Besides, some parents find that the males are more proper to take education than the females; likewise, the females will feel difficult to learn than the males (Fuller, 2009), although, if compared, the achievable academic performance is not far different (Bank, 2007). In aspects of computer mastering job (Scherer and Siddiq, 2015) and mathematic (Samuelsson and Samuelsson, 2016), the males have higher self-efficacy than the females; on the other hand, in the educational aspect, the females will have higher self-efficacy than the males (Sak, 2015). Even, teacher profession is perceived as a feminine profession (Martin, Nickels, and Sharp-Grier, 2017); (Mackinlay, 2016). Self-efficacy forms through a social learning process and continues during life range. The older has more experiences. Moreover, the senior student has longer professional formation experience (Demirtas, 2018). Types of achievable experiences will also affect the formation of reliance sense of self-competency to do tasks as a teacher.

Motivation as teacher

Motivation as a teacher is one very important aspect of the educational process for teacher candidates. Generally, motivation is usually defined as internal condition generating, directing, and maintaining behavior (Woolfolk, 2016). Thus, motivation as a teacher is associated with everything motivating the individual to select teacher profession; furthermore, what are factors making individual interested in and become individual having attention focus on teacher profession, as well as what can make individual select and stay in the teaching profession. About it, motivation as a teacher requires reason why one decides to do a thing (achievable experiences are associated with teacher profession), consistency of student to select and focus on teacher profession, as well as how does a student try to continue the activities when dealing with a challenge or social disorder, and social effect (Dornyei and Ushioda, 2011). Therefore, motivation as a teacher includes intrinsic motives (enthusiasm, competency, performance, etc.), extrinsic motives (aspects of family, profit/benefit, social status, etc.) and altruistic motives (social support for society, working with children and adults, etc.) (Brookhart and Freeman, 1992). Motivation as a teacher has also difference from gender in both intrinsic-academic motives (HakanMunire, 2014), and extrinsic motives – higher salary (Han, Borgonovi, and Guerriero, 2020), and female is more motivated due to academic performance motivation (Kusnierz, Rogowska, and Pavlova, 2020).

Research problem

The number of female teacher candidates dominates teacher education schools. They dominate the social humanities department. It is questionable whether their quality of motivation, self-efficacy, and perception as a teacher is better than male students, as well as from the perspective of their department.

Research hypothesis

Based on the literature review, the research hypothesis is proposed as follows: motivation as a teacher for female students is higher than male students, self-efficacy as a teacher for female students is higher than for

male students, and the perception of being a teacher for female students is higher than for male students, especially in the social and humanities department.

Method

This study is a quantitative study with a comparative study type. Study respondents were students studying at the State University of Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Samples were taken by giving *google form* to all students studying in one month, and 758 samples of students were gained. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the samples.

Table 1. Characteristics of Samples

No.	Aspect	Quantity and Percentage								
		1.	Age	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
		25 (3.3)	264 (34.8)	254 (33.5)	132 (17.4)	47 (6.2)	11 (1.5)	10 (1.3)	2 (0.3)	13 (1.7)
2.	Gender	Male				Female				
		144 (19%)				614 (81%)				
3	Semester	I		III		V		VII		IX
		415 (54.7)		201 (26.5)		117 (15.4)		12 (1.6)		12 (1.6)
4	Department	Exact				Social Humanity				
		179 (23.6)				579 (76.4)				

This study used the instrument of motivation as a teacher, self-efficacy as a teacher, and perception as a teacher. The instrument was adopted from *Factors Influencing Teaching Choice (FIT-Choice) Scale* (Nesje, Brandmo, and Berger, 2017) used to collect data of motivation as teacher and perception as a teacher, whereas self-efficacy as teacher adopted Ohio State Teacher Efficacy Scale (Tschannen-Moran and Hoy, 2001b). Therefore, the study instrument consisted of three types, namely, the scale of motivation as a teacher, the scale of self-efficacy as a teacher, and the scale of perception as a teacher. Choice alternative consisted of seven choices ranging from very consistent with student's condition to very inconsistent with student's condition. The data were analyzed by two-way ANOVA, to see differences in motivation, self-efficacy, and perception as teachers based on gender and department.

Results and Discussion

Results of data analysis

The collected data were analyzed to firstly find differences from motivation as teacher-reviewed from gender and department using two-way analysis of variance. Table 2 shows the summarized results of the analysis.

Table 2 Summary of Two-Way Anova for Data of motivation as Teacher

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	27.769 ^a	3	9.256	13.421	.000	.051
Intercept	10078.592	1	10078.592	14613.636	.000	.951
A	10.748	1	10.748	15.585	.000	.020
B	20.649	1	20.649	29.940	.000	.038
A * B	5.575	1	5.575	8.083	.005	.011
Error	520.011	754	.690			
Total	23039.609	758				
Corrected Total	547.780	757				

^a R Squared = .051 (Adjusted R Squared = .047)

Where:

A Gender	B Department
A1: Female	B1: Social Humanity
A2: Male	B2: Exact

The following can describe table 2 of *two-way* ANOVA: There is a significant difference in motivation as teacher viewed from gender, shown by inter A F_{count} of 15.585 with a *p-value* of 0.000 found $p < 0.05$. As seen from the mean score; motivation as a teacher in the females (5.54) is higher than the males (5.45). It indicates that motivation as a teacher in female students is higher than the of male students.

There is a significant difference in motivation as teachers viewed from the department, shown by inter $B_{F_{count}}$ of 29.940 with a *p-value* of 0.000 found $p < 0.05$. As seen from the mean score; motivation as a teacher in the students with social humanity department (5.53) is higher than students with the exact department (5.18). It indicates that motivation as a teacher in the students with social humanity department is higher than students with exact department. Moreover, there is an interaction between gender and department to motivation as a teacher; it is shown by Inter AB F_{count} of 8.083 with a *p-value* of 0.005; found $p < 0.05$.

The second analysis of data to find differences from efficacy as teacher-reviewed from gender and department used *two-way* ANOVA. Table 3 shows a summary of the results.

Table 3 Summary of data *two-way* ANOVA results of efficacy as teacher

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	18.924 ^a	3	6.308	8.895	.000	.034
Intercept	9324.045	1	9324.045	13147.439	.000	.946
A	6.587	1	6.587	9.288	.002	.012
B	14.087	1	14.087	19.864	.000	.026
A * B	3.065	1	3.065	4.321	.038	.006
Error	534.730	754	.709			
Total	21152.855	758				
Corrected Total	553.654	757				

^a R Squared = .034 (Adjusted R Squared = .030)

Where:

A Gender	B Department
A1: Female	B1: Social Humanity
A2: Male	B2: Exact

Table 3 of *two-way* ANOVA describes as follows: there is a significant difference in efficacy as teacher-reviewed from gender, shown by inter A F_{count} of 9.288 with a *p-value* of 0.002 found $p < 0.05$. As seen from the mean score, efficacy as a teacher of the females (5.25) is higher than the males (5.05). It indicates that efficacy in the learning of female students is higher than the of male students.

There is a significant difference in efficacy as a teacher reviewed from the department, shown by the inter $B_{F_{count}}$ of 19.864 with a *p-value* of 0.000 found $p < 0.05$. As seen from the mean score; efficacy as a teacher of students with a department of social humanity (5.28) is higher than students with a department of exact (4.99). This result indicates that efficacy as a teacher of students with the social humanity department is higher than students with the exact department. There is an interaction between gender and the department to efficacy as a teacher; it is shown by the Inter AB F_{count} of 4.321 with a *p-value* of 0.038; found $p < 0.05$.

The third analysis of data was to find differences in perception as teachers reviewed from gender and department using *two-way* ANOVA. Table 4 shows a summary of the results.

Table 4 Summary of data *Two-Way Anova* of Perception as Teacher

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	38.482 ^a	3	12.827	24.129	.000	.088
Intercept	11054.711	1	11054.711	20794.697	.000	.965
A	15.024	1	15.024	28.261	.000	.036
B	27.107	1	27.107	50.990	.000	.063
A * B	6.063	1	6.063	11.404	.001	.015

Error	400.835	754	.532
Total	25343.046	758	
Corrected Total	439.317	757	

^a $R^2 = .088$ ($Adjusted\ R^2 = .084$)

Where:

A Gender	B Department
A1: Female	B1: Social Humanity
A2: Male	B2: Exact

Table 4 of *two-way* ANOVA results can describe as follows: there is a significant difference in perception as teacher-reviewed from gender, shown by inter A F_{count} of 28.261 with the perception of 0.000, found $p < 0.05$. As seen from the mean score; perception as a teacher of the females (5.79) is higher than the males (5.48). This result indicates that the perception of a teacher of the female students is higher than the male students.

There is a significant difference in perception as teacher-reviewed from the department, shown by inter BF_{count} of 50.990 with a p -value of 0.000, found $p < 0.05$. Seen from the mean score; perception as a teacher of the students with the social humanity department (5.83) is higher than the students with the exact department (5.42). This result indicates that perception as a teacher of students with social humanity is higher than students with exact department.

There is a significant difference in perception as teacher-reviewed from the department, shown by the inter BF_{count} of 50.990 with a p -value of 0.000, found $p < 0.05$. Seen from the mean score; perception as a teacher of students with social humanity department (5.83) is higher than students with the exact department (5.42). This result indicates that perception as a teacher of students with social humanity department is higher than students with exact department. There is an interaction between gender and department to the perception as a teacher; it is shown by the inter BF_{count} of 11.404 with a p -value of 0.038; found $p < 0.05$.

Discussion

The difference from motivation as teacher-reviewed from gender and department

This study proves that there is a significant difference between motivation as a teacher between the female students and male students; female students have a higher motivation than male students. This condition can be explained in the following cultural context. Total female teachers dominating the teacher profession in Indonesia indicate that the teaching profession as a profession is identic to the females. The females dominate the school in a professional job, and teaching can be described as a feminine profession. The educational profession the females dominated also occurred in England and German (Baster, 1997). The teacher profession is feminine (Johnson, 2008). It is unarguable that female and male students have interest tendencies or different attractions.

This study indicates that there significant difference in motivation as a teacher between students with the social humanity department and students with the exact department; students with the social humanity department have a higher motivation than students with the exact department. A similar was also expressed from the results of a study indicating that department difference affected motivation to be a teacher (Bilim, 2014), but there is no student motivation difference affected by student semester status (*first year, sophomore, third years, etc.*) (Topkaya and Uztosun, 2012). It is caused by values that the students found different from a different department.

This study indicates that there is significant interaction between gender and department to motivation as a teacher. Female students with the social humanity department have the highest motivation; followed by male students with social humanity department; furthermore, followed by female and male students with social humanity and exact departments. This study has indicated that the teacher profession increased feminine values (Tomsik, 2017); however, it seemed that the teaching profession did not only increase femininity but also human values. Therefore, students with a social department background have a higher motivation than students with exact department. It means that type of the taken departmental science also gave color as a motivator in choosing the selected profession.

The difference from self-efficacy as teacher-reviewed from types of gender and department

This study indicates that there is a significant difference from efficacy as a teacher between female students and male students; female students have higher efficacy than male ones. Public opinion of society is similar to a diligent mother's image, sample homemaker, and perfect females (Stanonik, 2015). It has an impact on public opinion indicating that a teaching job is more appropriate for females so that this social support has

flowed positive energy suggesting that the females are more able to do the job as teachers. The condition motivates the development of the females' efficacy, including students (Bandura, 1997).

This study indicates that there is a significant difference in learning between students with the social humanity department and students with the exact department; students with the social humanity department have higher efficacy than students with the exact department. Self-efficacy can be achieved anywhere and anytime, depending on the situation in which the individuals exist. In general, self-efficacy forms due to the process of learning adaptation in which the individuals exist. The longer the individuals work in a division, the ones' self-efficacy is also higher in a specific job division. However, it does not make one's self-efficacy high because the possibility of their competency to adapt is weak. It also highly depends on how the individuals deal with success and failure facing them during the performance of the job (Bandura, 1997). Likewise, the educational program and department the students took gradually formed personal efficacy values according to the department the students took respectively (Pendergast, Garvis, and Keogh, 2011).

This study indicates that there is significant interaction between gender and department in learning. The female students with the social humanity department have the highest efficacy; followed by male students with the social humanity department, furthermore followed by the female students with the exact department and male students with exact department. The following sources affect the self-efficacy of students as teachers alone: experiences to the master of (functioning as competency indicator); verbal persuasion (verbal effect on competency the students feel); representation experiences (modeling and technique observation); and emotional enthusiasm (associated with the felt competency affecting process and results of tried tasks). The four sources experienced cognitive processing that determined how information sources would weigh and affect desirable teaching tasks. Experiences to the master are found the strongest effect because these give authentic proof of one's performance in a teaching situation (Bandura, 1997). Successful performance of a student for teacher candidate causes increasing in self-efficacy, whereas failure causes decreasing in self-efficacy. When students develop experiences to the master of, leading to the accumulation of increasing in students' self-efficacy, they rely on this as memory and interpretation of similar teaching experiences in the past time.

The difference from perception as teacher-reviewed from gender and department

This study has indicated that there is a significant difference from perception as a teacher between female students and male ones; female students have higher perception than male ones. It occurs because total female teachers are dominant to give a picture to the people regarding the professional figure in the community. If males dominate the teaching profession in the state, then the people will perceive it as a male profession; on the other hand, if the females dominate the teaching profession in the state, then the people also will perceive it as a female profession. Such a condition is very rational for Indonesia because the total teachers in Indonesia were 3,247,351 teachers, consisting of 974,709 (30.02%) male teachers and 2,272,642 (69.98%) teachers. This fact indicates that the females dominated the majority of teachers so that the formed perception in the community was also similar. Similar study results indicate that male students tended to expect to work as teachers in states with a higher representation of male teachers, vice versa (Han et. al., 2020). The study results also suggest a similar thing indicating that there is a different perception of students for teacher profession reviewed from gender (Herwin, 2011).

This study indicates that there is a significant difference from perception as a teacher between students with social humanity department and students with the exact department; the students with social humanity department have better perception than students with exact department. It is consistent with studies conducted in students of teacher candidates in Turkey (Balyer, 2017), and also in students of the SanataDarma University of Yogyakarta, Indonesia, stating that there is perception difference of students for teacher profession reviewed from department or study program (Herwin, 2011). The perception difference of students for teacher education profession reviewed from department and study program was caused by each study program having various activities and goal formulation. Each department or study program developed various efforts through various learning activities in the offered courses. In this case, the offered courses are consistent with goals formulated by the department or study program to generate competent alumni in their sciences. Teacher profession education is organized to anticipate the need for new increasing teachers and succession of retired teachers.

This study indicates that there is significant interaction between gender and department to perception as a teacher. Female students with the social humanity department have the highest perception; followed by male students with the social humanity department; furthermore followed by female students with the exact department and male students with the exact department. The results of the study are consistent with what was suggested in Turkey indicating that gender is a significant predictor of a professional ethic of a pre-service teacher in teaching, and indicating that females have a more significant ethical perception of the teaching profession than males. The results also indicate that, when gender is used as a covariate, analysis indicates that the teaching department is a significant predictor of perception for a pre-service teacher on professional ethics in teaching (Gelmez-Burakgazi, Can, and Coskun, 2020). The other results of a study using samples of students of

the SanataDarma University of Yogyakarta, Indonesia, indicating that gender and department or study program affected the perception of students as teachers (Herwinm 2011). Likewise, it is not fully consistent with other studies conducted in Turkey indicating that indeed there is the effect of the department on perception as a teacher, but there is no effect if seen from gender (Balyer, 2017). For the reasons, these need further studies.

Conclusion

The results of the study have indicated that there is a significant difference between motivation as a teacher, efficacy as a teacher, and perception as a teacher between female students and male students. Furthermore, female students have higher motivation as a teacher, efficacy as a teacher, and perception as a teacher than male ones. It indicates that female students dominate the teacher profession in internal psychological aspects and the reality of more female teachers. Social humanity (non-exact) has teacher candidates with higher motivation as a teacher, efficacy as a teacher, and perception as a teacher. Female students with the social humanity department have the best motivation as a teacher, self-efficacy as a teacher, and perception as a teacher, followed by male students with social humanity department, furthermore followed by female students with the exact department and male students with exact department.

Recommendations

Considering the importance of motivation as a teacher, self-efficacy as a teacher, and the perception of being a teacher in the process of forming the teaching profession, it is necessary to develop, maintain, and improve the psychological aspects of student teacher candidates. Further research is needed on the influence of gender and department on student perceptions as teachers. It is necessary to pay attention to various motivators to become a teacher, this is very important for a student to remain consistent and committed as a prospective teacher. Selection of prospective teachers should pay attention to various psychological aspects of prospective teachers such as motivation as a teacher, self-efficacy as a teacher, and perceptions of being a teacher because these have a significant correlation with various aspects of a teacher's performance.

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References

- Aszlan, G. (2011). Gender perceptions of preservice teachers. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanity Studies*, 3(2), 241–254.
- Balyer, A. (2017). Pre-service teachers' perceptions of their competency for the teaching profession. *Cumhuriyet International Journal of Education*, 6(2), 230–248.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy, the exercise of control*. New York: WH Freeman and Company.
- Bank, B. J. (Ed.). (2007). *Gender and education, an encyclopedia* (Volume I a). London: Praeger. <https://doi.org/10.1177/009430610903800228>
- Basten, C. (1997). A Feminised Profession: Women in the teaching profession. *Educational Studies*, 23(1), 55–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305569970230104>
- Bilim, I. (2014). Pre-service elementary teachers' motivations to become a teacher and its relationship with teaching self-efficacy. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 152, 653–661. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.09.258>
- Brookhart, S. M., and Freeman, D. J. (1992). Characteristics of Entering Teacher Candidates. *Review of Educational Research*, 62(1), 37–60. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543062001037>
- Demirtaş, V. Y. (2018). A study on teacher candidates' self-efficacy, motivation, and affection levels for children. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 6(12), 111. <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v6i12.3661>
- Dörnyei, Z., and Ushioda, E. (2011). *Teaching and researching motivation* (2nd Edt). Harlow: Pearson.
- Feldman, R. S. (2011). *Understanding psychology* (Tenth Edit). New York: McGraw-Hill Companies.
- Fuller, C. (2009). *Sociology, gender, and educational aspirations*. London: Continuum International Publishing Group. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2017.1327630>
- Gelmez-Burakgazi, S., Can, I., and Coşkun, M. (2020). Exploring pre-service teachers' perceptions about professional ethics in teaching: Do gender, major, and academic achievement matter? *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 16(4), 213–228. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2020.268.14>

- Hakan, K., and Münire, E. (2014). Academic motivation: gender, domain, and grade differences. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 143, 708–715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.07.469>
- Han, S. W., Borgonovi, F., and Guerriero, S. (2020). Why don't more boys want to become teachers? The effect of a gendered profession on students' career expectations. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 103(July), 101645. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2020.101645>
- Herwin, M. (2011). *Persepsi mahasiswa terhadap program pendidikan profesi guru ditinjau dari jenis kelamin , program studi dan prestasi akademik*. Universitas Sanata Dharma.
- Johnson, S. P. (2008). The status of male teachers in public education today. *Center for Evaluation & Education Policy*, 6(4), 1–12.
- Kemenristekdikti. (2019). *Statistik Pendidikan Tinggi (Higher Education Statistics) 2019*. Jakarta: Pusdatin Iptek Dikti.
- Kuśnierz, C., Rogowska, A. M., and Pavlova, I. (2020). Examining gender differences, personality traits, academic performance, and motivation in Ukrainian and polish students of physical education: A cross- cultural study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(16), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17165729>
- Mackinlay, E. (2016). *Teaching and learning like a feminist : storying our experiences in higher education*. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers.
- Martin, J. L., Nickels, A. E., and Sharp-Grier, M. (Eds.). (2017). *Feminist pedagogy, practice, and activism*. New York: Taylor & Francis Group. Retrieved from <http://library1.nida.ac.th/termpaper6/sd/2554/19755.pdf>
- Nesje, K., Brandmo, C., and Berger, J. L. (2017). Motivation to Become a Teacher: a Norwegian Validation of the Factors Influencing Teaching Choice Scale. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 62(6), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2017.1306804>
- Nzilano, J. L. (2013). Pre-Service teachers' teaching competencies: the Experience of practicing teaching in secondary schools and teacher colleges. *African Journal of Teacher Education*, 3(1), 1–21.
- Pendergast, D., Garvis, S., and Keogh, J. (2011). Pre-service student-teacher self-efficacy beliefs: an insight into the making of teachers. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 36(12), 46–58. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2011v36n12.6>
- Pop, R. (2015). Understanding Pre-service Trainees' Perceptions of their Teacher Training Experience. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 209(July), 378–382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.11.207>
- Ratnawati, D., Sulistyorini, and Abidin, A. Z. (2019). Kesetaraan gender tentang pendidikan laki-laki dan perempuan. *Jurnal Harkat*, 15(1), 10–23.
- Sak, R. (2015). Comparison of self-efficacy between male and female pre-service early childhood teachers. *Early Child Development and Care*, 185(10), 1629–1640. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2015.1014353>
- Samuelsson, M., and Samuelsson, J. (2016). Gender differences in boys' and girls' perception of teaching and learning mathematics. *Open Review of Educational Research*, 3(1), 18–34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23265507.2015.1127770>
- Scherer, R., and Siddiq, F. (2015). Revisiting teachers' computer self-efficacy: A differentiated view on gender differences. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 53, 48–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.06.038>
- Schunk, D. H., and DiBenedetto, M. K. (2016). Self-efficacy theory in education. In K. R. Wentzel and D. B. Miele (Eds.), *Handbook of motivation at school* (pp. 1–532). New York: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315773384>
- Shinde, M. B., and Karekatti, T. K. (2012). Pre-service teachers' belief about teaching English to primary school children. *International Journal of Instruction*, 5(1), 69–86.
- Stanonik, M. (2015). Education and feminization of the teaching profession. In M. Godawa and S. Gerjoli (Eds.), *Faces of women : in search of positive prospects* (pp. 113–123). Krakow. <https://doi.org/10.15633/9788374384919.10>
- Tomšik, R. (2017). Motivations for Choosing Teaching as a Career. *Paidagogos - Journal of Education in Contexts*, 2017(1), 1–10.
- Topkaya, E. Z., and Uztosun, M. S. (2012). Choosing teaching as a career: motivations of pre-service English teachers in turkey. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 3(1), 126–134. <https://doi.org/10.4304/jltr.3.1.126-134>
- Tschannen-Moran, M., and Hoy, A. W. (2001). Teacher efficacy: capturing an elusive construct. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(17), 783–805.
- UNESCO. (2015). *A guide for gender equality in teacher education policy and practices*. Paris: United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization.
- Williams, M., and Burden, R. L. (1997). *Psychology for language teachers* (12th). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3588203>

Woolfolk, A. (2016). *Educational psychology* (Thirteenth). London: Pearson.

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